

Collembola of India- An Updated Checklist

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Abstract

An updated checklist of Collembola from India is provided with their distribution. A total of 342 species under 113 genera grouped in 20 families are listed. 307 species belong to 97 genera of order Poduromorpha + Entomobryomorpha and 35 species belongs to 16 genera of order Symphypleona. Additionally, a new distributional data have been provided for Seventy eight species recorded from different states of India.

Keywords: *Collembola, species, checklist, India.*

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Introduction

The Collembola, commonly called “spring-tails”, are small, entognathous, wingless hexapods possessing a spring-like forked jumping organ, the furcula, underneath the fourth abdominal segment. There are about 8800 described species of Collembola worldwide (Bellinger *et al.*, 2018).

The first Indian species of collembola from Malabar hill regions was published by Ritter (1910). Thereafter, Imms (1912), Carpenter (1917, 1924), Handschin (1925, 1929), Bonet (1930), Brown (1932), Mukherjee (1932), Denis, (1936, 1947), Baijal (1955a, b, 1956; 1958, 1971a, b), Baijal and Verma (1986), Paliwal and Baijal (1985), Tyagi and Baijal (1978, 1982), Salmon (1956a, b, 1957a, b, 1958, 1963, 1965, 1969, 1970), Arora and Singh (1962), Choudhuri and Roy (1965), Yosii (1966a, b), Prabhoo (1970, 1971a, b, c) Prabhoo and Muraleedharan (1980), Cassaganu (1980, 1988, 1990), Mitra (1966a, b, 1967, 1973a, b, 1974a, b, 1975, 1976a, b), Hazra *et al.* (2003, 2004, 2006a, b, 2007), Hazra and Mandal (2007, 2010, 2012), Mandal (2011, 2013, 2014, 2018), Mandal and Hazra (2004, 2005, 2009), Mandal and Suman (2013a, b, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017) contributed to the knowledge of Indian Collembola. Recently, Baquero, Mandal and Jordana (2014, 2015), Hazra and Mandal (2015), Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya (2016, 2017)

are some of the researchers who have substantially added a number of species to the Collembola from India. Indian fauna of Collembola is represented by 342 species of 113 genera belonging to 20 families. Out of which, Poduromorpha + Entomobryomorpha consists of 307 species in 97 genera in 12 families: Neanuridae (55 species of 24 genera), Tullbergidae (6 species of 3 genera), Brachystomellidae (3 species of one genus), Hypogastruridae (23 species of 5 genera), Onychiuridae (5 species of 4 genera), Oncopoduridae (one species of one genus), Odontellidae (3 species of 2 genera), Isotomidae (42 species of 20 genera), Orchesellidae (12 species of 4 genera), Entomobryidae (83 species of 17 genera), Paronellidae (69 species of 15 genera), Tomoceridae (5 species of one genus) and Symphypleona consists of 35 species in 16 genera in 8 families: Neelidae (one species of one genus), Sminthuridae (12 species of 5 genera), Katiannidae (one species of one genus), Dicyrtomidae (5 species of 2 genera), Collophoridae (2 species of one genus), Bourletiellidae (4 species of 2 genera), Sminthurididae (8 species of 3 genera) and Arrhopalitidae (one species of one genus). The objective of this paper is to provide up to date list on Collembola fauna of India with distribution records.

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The Checklist

Detail synonymies for the names listed here are available on the website (www.collembola.org). Distribution records of species are based on published work of previous authors and recent publication of the author. The symbol (*) indicates new distributional record from different states of India for the species.

Class Collembola Lubbock, 1870

Order Poduromorpha Börner, 1913, sensu D'Haese, 2002

Superfamily Neanuroidea Massoud, 1967

Family Neanuridae Börner, 1901 sensu Yosii, 1956

Subfamily Frieseinae Massoud, 1967

Genus *Friesea* Von Dalla Torre, 1895

Friesea excelsa Denis, 1936

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir, Kerala, West Bengal).

Friesea maxima Baijal, 1956

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Friesea yosii, Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Subfamily Neanurinae Börner, 1901, Sensu Cassagnau, 1989

Tribe Lobellini Cassagnau, 1983

Genus *Adbiloba* Stach, 1951

Adbiloba sikkimensis (Yosii, 1966)

Distribution: India (Sikkim).

Genus *Blasconura* Cassagnau, 1983

Blasconura toda Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Blasconura palniensis Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Palni, Tamil Nadu).

Blasconura prabhooi Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Blasconura sholica Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Blasconura anamalaisis Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Anamalai, Tamil Nadu).

Genus *Calvinura* Cassagnau, 1988

Calvinura reducta Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Anamalai, Tamil Nadu).

Genus *Gnatholonche* Börner, 1906

Gnatholonche intermedia (Imms, 1912) Stach, 1951

Distribution: India (Naini Tal, Uttarakhand).

Gnatholonche polychaetosa Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Darjeling, West Bengal).

Genus *Himalmeria* Cassagnau, 1984

Himalmeria ornata Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Darjeling, West Bengal).

Himalmeria karmapa Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Sikkim).

Subgenus *Yetimeria* Cassagnau, 1984

Himalmeria (Y.) sikkimensis Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Sikkim).

Himalmeria (Y.) lama Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Darjeling, West Bengal).

Himalmeria (Y.) rostrata Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Darjeling, West Bengal).

Himalmeria (Y.) armata Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Sukna, West Bengal).

Himalmeria (Y.) lanata Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Singhlila National Park, Darjeling, West Bengal).

Himalmeria (Y.) spatulata Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Singhlila National Park, Darjeling, West Bengal).

Genus *Hyperlobella* Cassagnau, 1988

Hyperlobella kraepelini (Börner, C., 1906)

Cassagnau, P., 1988

Distribution: India (Kerala, Arunachal Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Maharashtra, Mizoram*).

Genus *Inameria* Cassagnau, 1983

Inameria corallina (Imms, 1912) Cassagnau, 1983

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Lobella* Börner, C., 1906

Subgenus *Protolobella* Cassagnau, 1983

Lobella (P.) assamensis Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (Assam, Mizoram*).

Subgenus *Lobella* Cassagnau, 1983

Lobella (L.) malabarica Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Lobella (L.) maxillaris Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (Botanic Garden, West Bengal).

Genus *Neanura* MacGillivray, 1893

Neanura muscorum (Templeton, 1836) Cart, 1899

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Nilgirella* Cassagnau, 1983

Nilgirella indica (Handschin, 1929) Cassagnau, 1983

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Nilgirella longiseta Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Nilgirella palniensis Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Palni, Tamil Nadu).

Nilgirella piljainae Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Tribe Paleonurini Cassagnau, P., 1989

Genus *Paleonura* Cassagnau, P., 1982

Paleonura lonavlana (Yosii, 1966) Cassagnau, 1982

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Paleonura siva (Yosii, 1966) Cassagnau, 1982

Distribution: India (Botanic Garden, West Bengal)

Paleonura macronychia Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Paleonura badaga Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Paleonura barbata Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Palni, Tamil Nadu).

Paleonura decorata Cassagnau, 1988

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Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Paranura* Axelson, 1902

Paranura tamul Cassagnau, P., 1983

Distribution: India (Palni, Tamil Nadu).

Paranura garoensis Cassagnau, 1991

Distribution: India (Meghalaya).

Paranura coenobita Cassagnau, 1991

Distribution: India (Sikkim).

Paranura squamosa Cassagnau, 1991

Distribution: India (Darjeling, West Bengal).

Genus *Parvatinura* Cassagnau, 1984

Parvatinura loebli Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Darjeling, West Bengal).

Parvatinura colcheni Cassagnau, 1984

Distribution: India (Darjeling, West Bengal).

Genus *Pronura* Delamare Deboutteville, 1953

Pronura indiana Salmon, 1969

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Assam, Uttar Pradesh*).

Genus *Protanura* Börner, 1900

Protanura carpenteri Mukherjee, 1932

Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Genus *Singalimeria* Cassagnau, 1984

Singalimeria pachyderma Cassagnau, P., 1984

Distribution: India (Singhila National Park, Darjeling, West Bengal).

Genus *Tamulmeria* Cassagnau, 1988

Tamulmeria callipygos Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Ootacamund, Tamil Nadu).

Tamulmeria keralensis Cassagnau, 1988

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Womersleya* Denis, 1948

Womersleya marhia Baijal, 1958

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Subfamily Pseudochorutinae Börner, 1906

Genus *Cephalochorutes* Bedos and Deharverg, 1991

Cephalochorutes pillaii (Prabhoo, 1971) Bedos and Deharverg, 1991

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Ceratrimeria* Börner, C., 1906

Ceratrimeria indica (Handschin, 1929) Massoud, 1967

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Genus *Oudemansia* Schott, 1893

Oudemansia coerulea Schött, 1893

Distribution: India (Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu).

Genus *Pseudachorutes* Tullberg, 1871

Pseudachorutes anomalus Imms, 1912

Distribution: India (Kurseong, West Bengal).

Pseudachorutes periyarensis Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Pseudachorutes ponmudiensis (Prabhoo, 1971)

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Subfamily Uchidanurinae Salmon, 1964

Genus *Assamanura* Cassagnau, 1980

Assamanura besucheti Cassagnau, 1980

Distribution: India (Khasi Hills, Meghalaya).

Family Brachystomellidae Stach, 1949

Genus *Brachystomella* Agren, 1903

Brachystomella contorta Denis, 1931

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Brachystomella surendrai Goto, 1961

Distribution: India (Rajasthan).

Brachystomella terraefolia Salmon, 1944

Distribution: India (Kerala, Maharashtra)

Family Tullbergiidae Bagnall, 1935

Genus *Mesaphorura* Börner, 1901

Mesaphorura choudhuriai Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Maharashtra).

Mesaphorura intermedia Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Paratullbergia* Womersley, 1930

Paratullbergia indica Salmon, 1965

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Paratullbergia salmoni Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Paratullbergia trivandranana Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Prabhergia* Salmon, 1965

Prabhergia nayarii Salmon, 1965

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Superfamily Hypogastruroidea Salmon, 1964

Family Hypogastruridae Börner, 1906

Genus *Acherontiella* Absolon, 1913

Acherontiella bougisi Cassagnau and Delamare, 1955

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Ceratophysella* Börner in Brohmer, 1932

Ceratophysella indica (Salmon, 1956)

Distribution: India (Sikkim, West Bengal*).

Ceratophysella indovaria (Salmon, 1970)

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Mizoram, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, West Bengal*, Andhra Pradesh*, Uttar Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Himachal Pradesh *, Jharkhand*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Ceratophysella communis (Folsom, 1897)

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh*, Uttar Pradesh*).

Ceratophysella armata (Nicolet, 1842) Börner, 1932

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).

Ceratophysella narkandae (Baijal, 1955)

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Genus *Hypogastrura* Bourlet, 1839

Subgenus *Hypogastrura* Bourlet, 1839

Hypogastrura baltica Tyagi and Baijal, 1982

Distribution: India (Bijnor, Uttar Pradesh).

Hypogastrura katraensis Tyagi and Baijal, 1982

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

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Hypogastrura prabhoi Bhattacharjee, 1985
Distribution: India (Meghalaya).
Hypogastrura sonapani Baijal, H.N., 1958
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).
Hypogastrura temarpurensis Tyagi and Baijal, 1982
Distribution: India (Bijnor, Uttar Pradesh).
Hypogastrura unguiculata Mitra, 1966
Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).
Hypogastrura manubrialis (Tullberg, 1869) Linnaniemi, 1912
Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).
Hypogastrura rangkuli Martynova, 1975
Distribution: India (Ladak).
Hypogastrura nivicola (Fitch, 1847) Yosii, 1960
Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).
Hypogastrura consanguinea (Folsom, 1924) Handschin, 1928
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Genus *Willemia* Borner, 1901
Willemia delamarei Prabho, 1971
Distribution: India (Kerala).
Willemia setonychia Prabho, 1971
Distribution: India (Kerala).
Genus *Xenylla* Tullberg, 1869
Xenylla hadialii Baijal, 1955
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).
Xenylla obscura Imms, 1912
Distribution: India (Sikkim, Manipur, Arunachal Pradesh, Mizoram, Nagaland, Himachal Pradesh*, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, West Bengal*, Uttar Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Andhra Pradesh*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).*
Xenylla reducta Prabho, 1971
Distribution: India (Kerala).
Xenylla sincta Baijal, 1956
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir*).*
Xenylla welchi Folsom, 1916
Distribution: India (Kerala).
Superfamily Onychiuroidea sensu D'Haese, 2002
Family Onychiuridae Borner, 1901
Genus *Allonychiurus* Yoshii, 1995
Allonychiurus indicus (Choudhuri and Roy, 1965) Pomorski, 2002
Distribution: India (West Bengal, Maharashtra*).*
Genus *Onychiurus* Gervais, 1841
Onychiurus bhatti Yosii, 1963
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).
Genus *Protaphorura* Absolon, 1901
Protaphorura kultia (Baijal, 1956) Salmon, 1964
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).
Tribe Thalassaphorurini Pomorski, 1998
Genus *Thalassaphorura* Bagnall, 1949
Thalassaphorura clayae (Salmon, 1958) Pomorski, 2002

Distribution: India (Sikkim).
Thalassaphorura ghatensis (Prabho, 1971) Pomorski, 2002
Distribution: India (Kerala).

Family Odontellidae Massoud, 1967
Genus *Spinanurida* Salmon, 1969
Spinanurida mandibulata Salmon, 1969
Distribution: India (Sikkim).
Genus *Superodontella* Stach, 1949
Superodontella altitudina (Salmon, 1969)
Distribution: India (Sikkim).
Superodontella macronychia (Prabho, 1971)
Distribution: India (Kerala).

Order Entomobryomorpha Borner, 1913, sensu Soto-Adames et al., 2008
Superfamily Tomoceroidea Szeptycki, 1979
Family Oncopoduridae Carl and Lebedinsky, 1905
Genus *Oncopodura* Carl and Lebedinsky, 1905
Oncopodura indica Yosii, 1966
Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Family Tomoceridae Schaffer, 1896
Subfamily Tomocerinae Schaffer, 1896
Genus *Tomocerus* Nicolet, (1842)
Tomocerus mitrai Prabho and Muraleedharan, 1980
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Jammu and Kashmir*, Sikkim*).*
Tomocerus petalospinus Salmon, 1969
Distribution: India (Sikkim, Jammu and Kashmir*).*
Tomocerus serratospinus Salmon, 1941
Distribution: India (Sikkim).
Tomocerus vulgaris (Tullberg, 1871) Brook, 1883
Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).
Tomocerus ashoka Yosii and Ashraf, 1965
Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).

Superfamily Isotomoidea Szeptycki, 1979
Family Isotomidae Schaffer, 1896
Subfamily Anurophorinae Borner, 1901
Genus *Cryptopygus* Willem, 1901
Cryptopygus indicus Brown, 1932
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Cryptopygus tridentus (Handschin, 1929)
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Genus *Hemisotoma* Bagnall, 1949
Hemisotoma thermophila (Axelson, 1900) Bagnall, 1949
Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Kerala, West Bengal, Manipur, Assam, Odisha, Rajasthan, Sikkim*, Arunachal Pradesh*).*
Genus *Isotomodes* Axelson, 1907
Isotomodes dagamae Prabho, 1971

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Distribution: India (Kerala, West Bengal, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh).
Genus *Rhodanella* Salmon, 1945
Rhodanella fasciata (Carpenter, 1912)
Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, Manipur, Sikkim).

Subfamily Isotominae Schaffer, 1896

Genus *Aackia* Yosii, 1966

Aackia karakoramensis Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).

Genus *Axelsonia* Börner, 1906

Axelsonia nitida (Folsom, 1899) Börner, 1906

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, West Bengal*, Odisha*).

Genus *Desoria* Agassiz and Nicolet, 1841

Desoria mazda Yosii, 1971

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Jammu and Kashmir*).

Desoria trispinata (Mac Gillivray, 1896) Mendoza Arviso, 1999

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Assam*, Nagaland*).

Desoria jayasrae Bhattacharjee, 1985

Distribution: India (Meghalaya, Assam).

Genus *Isotoma* Bourlet, 1839

Isotoma fasciata Börner, 1909

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Isotoma himalayana (Baijal, 1955)

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir).

Isotoma sarkundensis Baijal, 1958

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir).

Isotoma spinicauda Bonet, 1930

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir).

Isotoma plumosa (Salmon, 1969)

Distribution: India (Sikkim).

Genus *Isotomiella* Bagnall, 1939

Isotomiella minor (Schaeffer, 1896) Yosii, 1939

Distribution: India (Kerala, West Bengal, Odisha, Maharashtra, Arunachal Pradesh*, Rajasthan, Manipur*, Tripura*, Sikkim).

Genus *Isotomurus* Börner, 1903

Isotomurus balteatus (Reuter, 1876) Handschin, 1929

Distribution: India (Kerala, West Bengal, Odisha, Maharashtra*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Manipur*, Tripura*, Andhra Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Jharkhand*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Isotomurus ciliatus Stach, 1947

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Odisha, Maharashtra*).

Isotomurus palustris (Muller, 1776) Börner, 1906

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Odisha, Maharashtra*).

Isotomurus jharkhandensis Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya, 2017

Distribution: India (Jharkhand).

Isotomurus dhanbadensis Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya, 2017

Distribution: India (Jharkhand).

Isotomurus indicus Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya, 2017

Distribution: India (Jharkhand).

Isotomurus sahebganjensis Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya, 2017

Distribution: India (Jharkhand).

Genus *Parisotoma* Bagnall, 1940

Parisotoma notabilis (Schaffer, 1896) Bagnall, 1940

Distribution: India (Sikkim).

Genus *Procerura* Salmon, 1941

Procerura indica (Baijal, 1958) Greenslade, 2003

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir*).

Procerura transequatoria (Salmon, 1969) Greenslade, 2003

Distribution: India (Sikkim).

Subfamily Proisotominae Stach, 1947

Genus *Appendisotoma* Stach, 1947

Appendisotoma tridentata (Baijal, 1958) Potapov, 2001

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Genus *Ballistura* Börner, 1906

Ballistura bengalensis Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Maharashtra, Kerala).

Ballistura fitchi (Denis, 1933)

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Genus *Folsomia* Willem, 1902

Folsomia baijali Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Folsomia santokhi (Baijal, 1958)

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Folsomia octoculata Handschin, 1925

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Folsomia fimetaria (Linn.) Handschin, 1929

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Folsomia candida Willem, 1902

Distribution: India (Meghalaya).

Genus *Folsomides* Stach, 1922

Folsomides parvulus Stach, 1922

Distribution: India (Kerala, Maharashtra, West Bengal).

Genus *Folsomina* Denis, 1931

Folsomina onychiurina Denis, 1931

Distribution: India (Kerala, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh*).

Genus *Isotopenola* Potapov, Babenko, Fjellberg, and Greenslade, 2009

Isotopenola nilgiris (Denis, 1947) Potapov, Babenko, Fjellberg and Greenslade, 2009

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Genus *Proisotoma* Börner, 1901

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Proisotoma himalayana Baijal, 1958

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Uttar Pradesh*).

Proisotoma senetijohani Baijal and Chandra, 1970

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Proisotoma minuta (Tullberg, 1871) Börner, 1903

Distribution: India (Kerala, Maharashtra).

Proisotoma pakurensis Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya, 2017

Distribution: India (Jharkhand).

Genus *Scutisotoma* Bagnall, 1949

Scutisotoma ladaki (Denis, 1936) Potapov, Babenko, and Fjellberg, 2006

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir).

Superfamily Entomobryoidea Womersley, 1934, sensu Zhang et al., 2015

Family Orchesellidae Börner, 1906

Subfamily Orchesellinae Börner, 1906

Genus *Orchesellides* Bonet, 1930

Orchesellides crassus (Imms, 1912)

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh*).

Orchesellides boraoi Bonet, 1930

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).

Subfamily Heteromurinae Absolon & Kseneman, 1942

Tribe Heteromururini Mari Mutt, 1980

Genus *Alloscopus* Börner, 1906

Alloscopus aspinosus Prabhaoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Alloscopus spinosus Prabhaoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Alloscopus tetracanthus (Börner, 1906)

Distribution: India (Kerala, West Bengal).

Genus *Dicranocentrus* Schött, 1893

Dicranocentrus indicus Bonet, 1930

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, West Bengal, Nagaland*, Manipur*, Mizoram*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Uttar Pradesh*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Dicranocentrus cercifer (Imms, 1912) Mari Mutt, 1979

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Kerala, Jharkhand*)

Dicranocentrus singularis Mari Mutt and Bhattacharjee, 1980

Distribution: India (Meghalaya).

Dicranocentrus fraternus Mari Mutt and Bhattacharjee, 1980

Distribution: India (Meghalaya).

Dicranocentrus spinosus (Prabhaoo, 1971)

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Dicranocentrus stachi (Denis, 1925) Handschin, 1929

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Genus *Falcomurus* Mandal, 2018

Falcomurus chilikaensis Mandal, 2018

Distribution: India (Odisha).

Family Entomobryidae Schaffer, 1896

Subfamily Entomobryinae Schaffer, 1896

Genus *Entomobrya* Rondani, 1861

Entomobrya himalayensis (Baijal, 1955) Salmon, 1964

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh).

Entomobrya indica (Baijal, 1955)

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Entomobrya kultinalensis Baijal, 1958

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Entomobrya logisticta Baijal, 1958

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Entomobrya manii (Baijal, 1955) Salmon, 1964

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Entomobrya nigrita (Baijal, H. N., 1958)

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Entomobrya rohtangensis Baijal, 1958

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Entomobrya nivalis (Linnaeus, 1758) Agren, 1904

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir).

Entomobrya lampreyi (Salmon, 1957)

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Entomobrya diskittensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2014

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir).

Entomobrya ladakhi Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2014

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir).

Entomobrya choudhuria Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2014

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir).

Entomobrya mehtai Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2014

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir).

Entomobrya kajjirensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Entomobrya barogensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Genus *Himalanura* Baijal, H.N., 1958

Himalanura indica Baijal, H.N., 1958

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Himalanura baijali Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2014

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir).

Himalanura chailensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

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Himalanura himachalensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Genus *Homidia* Börner, C., 1906

Homidia cingula (Börner, C., 1906) Yosii, 1959

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh*, Himachal Pradesh*, Uttar Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Manipur*, Sikkim*, Mizoram*, Nagaland*, Odisha*).

Homidia lakhanpurensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Tribe Lepidocyrtini Yoshii and Yanyu*k*, 1989

Genus *Lepidocyrtoides* Schött, 1917

Lepidocyrtoides quatuordecimocellata Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Mesentotoma* Salmon, 1942

Mesentotoma hutchinsoni (Denis, 1936) Jordana, 2012

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir).

Genus: *Pseudosinella* Schaeffer, 1897

Pseudosinella petterseni Börner, 1901

Distribution: India (Kerala, Maharashtra).

Genus *Sinella* Brook, 1882

Subgenus *Sinella* Brook, 1882

Sinella curviseta Brook, 1882

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Jammu and Kashmir*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Assam*, Punjab*, Sikkim*, West Bengal, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Sinella siva (Imms, 1912) Chen and Christiansan, 1993

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Subgenus *Coecobrya* Yosii, 1956

Sinella (C.) montana Imms, 1912

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Tribe Willowsiini Yoshii and Yayuk, 1989

Genus *Willowsia* Shoebottom, 1917

Willowsia nigromaculata (Lubbock, 1873), Salmon, 1945

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Himachal Pradesh*).

Willowsia brahma (Imms, 1912)

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh*).

Willowsia jacobsoni (Börner, 1913) Stach, 1965

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir).

Willowsia kalatopensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Subfamily Lepidocyrtinae Wahlgren, 1906 Sensus Stach, 1955

Genus *Acanthurella* Börner, 1906

Acanthurella betlaensis Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya, 2016

Distribution: India (Jharkhand).

Genus *Lepidocyrtus* Bourlet, 1839

Lepidocyrtus exploratorius Carpenter, 1924

Distribution: India (Meghalaya, Maharashtra, West Bengal*).

Subgenus *Acrocyrtus* Yosii, 1959

Lepidocyrtus (A.) heterolepis Yosii, 1959

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Manipur*, Uttar Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, West Bengal*, Jharkhand*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Lepidocyrtus (A.) malayanus Yosii, 1959

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand*, West Bengal* Mizoram, Arunachal Pradesh*, Manipur*, Nagaland*, Sikkim*, Tripura*, Andhra Pradesh*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Lepidocyrtus (A.) cryptocephalus Handschin, 1929

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Lepidocyrtus (A.) cheni Pan, Chatterjee, and Zhang, 2011

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Lepidocyrtus (A.) himachalensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Subgenus *Allocyrtus* Yosii and Suhardjono, 1984

Lepidocyrtus (A.) lepidornatus (Handschin, 1930)

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh*).

Subgenus *Ascocyrtus* Yosii, 1963

Lepidocyrtus (A.) magnificus Carpenter, 1924

Distribution: India (Meghalaya, West Bengal, Arunachal Pradesh*, Manipur*, Mizoram*, Nagaland*, Sikkim*, Tripura*, Uttar Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Lepidocyrtus (A.) scaber Ritter, 1911

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal*).

Lepidocyrtus (A.) suborientalis Denis, 1948

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Subgenus *Cinctocyrtus* Yoshi, and Yayuk, 1989

Lepidocyrtus (C.) medius Schaeffer, 1898

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh*, Manipur*, Mizoram*, Nagaland*, Sikkim*, Tripura*, Uttar Pradesh*).

Lepidocyrtus (C.) kulluensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Subgenus *Lanocyrtus* Yoshii, and Yayuk, 1989

Lepidocyrtus (L.) caeruleicornis Bonet, 1930

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, West Bengal).

Lepidocyrtus (L.) pallidus Reuter, 1890

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Lepidocyrtus (L.) cyaneus Tullberg, 1871

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Manipur*, Jharkhand*).

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Lepidocyrtus (L.) absens Zhang, Chatterjee and Chen, 2009

Distribution: India (Andhra Pradesh).

Subgenus *Lepidocyrtus* Bourlet, 1839

Lepidocyrtus (L.) agraensis Baijal and Singha, 1971

Distribution: India (UttarPradesh).

Lepidocyrtus (L.) curvicollis (Bourlet, 1839) Bourlet, 1841

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand*, West Bengal*, Arunachal*, Andhra Pradesh*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Lepidocyrtus (L.) robustus Imms, 1912

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Lepidocyrtus (L.) orientalis Handschin, 1929

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Subgenus *Setogaster* Salmon, 1951

Lepidocyrtus (S.) indicus (Handschin, 1929) Wang, Chen, and Christianan, 2003

Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).

Lepidocyrtus (S.) manipuri (Salmon, 1969)

Distribution: India (Manipur).

Genus *Lepidiaphanus* Salmon, 1949

Lepidiaphanus kashmirensis Arora and Singh, 1962

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).

Genus *Pseudocyrtus* Salmon, 1956

Pseudocyrtus dentatus Prabhoo, 1967

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Pseudocyrtus salmoni Prabhoo, 1967

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Pseudocyrtus projectus Salmon, 1956

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Subfamily Seirinae Ssensu Deharverg, 2004

Genus *Corynothrix* Tullberg, 1877

Corynothrix borealis Tullberg, 1877

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir*)

Genus *Drepanosira* Bonet, 1942

Drepanosira frigida (Imms, 1912)

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand).

Drepanosira subornata (Denis, 1936) Bonet, 1942

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir, Uttar Pradesh*).

Drepanosira hussi Neuhertz, 1976

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh*).

Drepanosira raviensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Drepanosira shimlaensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Genus *Lepidosira* Schött, 1925

Lepidosira nilgiri (Denis, 1936)

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Lepidosira unguerrata Salmon, 1970

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Uttarakhand*, Arunachal Pradesh*).

Genus *Seira* Lubbock, 1869

Seira arunachala Mitra, 1975

Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh)

Seira lateralis Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Seira indica (Ritter, 1911) Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Kerala, West Bengal, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Nagaland, Uttar Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*, Jharkhand*, Andhra Pradesh*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Seira cooperi Handschin, 1929

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Seira indianicus (Paliwal and Baijal, 1985)

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Seira mandawericus (Paliwal and Baijal, 1985)

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Seira keethumensis (Paliwal and Baijal, 1985)

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Seira indra (Imms, 1912)

Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Seira cinerea Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Seira punctata (Ritter, 1911)

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Seira unifasciata (Denis, 1936)

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).

Seira delamarei Jacquemart, 1980

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir*).

Seira nidarensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2014

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir)

Seira hazrai Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2014

Distribution: India (Ladak, Jammu and Kashmir)

Seira prabhooi Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Seira simbalwaraensis Baquero, Mandal and Jordana, 2015

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Subfamily Willowsiinae Yoshi and Suhardjao, 1989

Genus *Janetschekbrya* Yosii, 1971

Janetschekbrya brahmidensis (Denis, 1936)

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).

Family Paronellidae Börner, 1913

Subfamily Cyphoderinae Börner, 1913, Ssensu Soto –Adams, 2008

Genus *Cyphoda* Delamare Debutteville, 1948

Cyphoda limboxiphia (Börner, 1913)

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Genus *Cyphoderodes* Silvestri, 1910

Cyphoderodes mitrai Yosii, 1987

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Cyphoderodes dubius Börner, 1913

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Cyphoderodes ceylonicus Silvestri, 1910

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Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Kerala*).

Genus *Cyphoderus* Nicolet, 1842
Cyphoderus albinus Nicolet, 1842
Distribution: India (Maharashtra).
Cyphoderus ganeensis Tyagi and Baijal, 1979
Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).
Cyphoderus javanus Börner, 1906
Distribution: India (West Bengal, Kerala, Rajasthan, Arunachal Pradesh*, Manipur*, Mizoram*, Sikkim*, Odisha*, Maharashtra*, Uttarakhand*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*)
Cyphoderus rubiae Baijal, 1955
Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).
Cyphoderus sarojinii Bhattacharjee, 1985
Distribution: India (Meghalaya).
Cyphoderus assimilis Börner, 1906
Distribution: India (Assam).
Cyphoderus indicus Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya, 2016
Distribution: India (Jharkhand).
Cyphoderus jharkhandensis Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya, 2016
Distribution: India (Jharkhand).
Genus *Delamarerus* Mitra, 1977
Delamarerus immsi Mitra, 1977
Distribution: India (Odisha, Maharashtra*, Andhra Pradesh*).

Genus *Pseudocyphoderus* Imms, 1912
Pseudocyphoderus annandalei Imms, 1912
Distribution: India (Odisha, Maharashtra*, Andhra Pradesh*).

Pseudocyphoderus squamicaudus Silvestri, 1917
Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Odisha*).

Genus *Serroderus* Delamare Deb. 1948
Serroderus tridenticulatus Denis, 1948
Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Subfamily Paronellinae Börner, 1913 sensu Soto-Adams et al., 2008

Tribe *Callyntrurini* Mitra, 1993
Genus *Callyntrura* Börner, 1906
Callyntrura escheri (Handschin, 1929)
Distribution: India (Anamalai, Tamil Nadu).
Callyntrura semiviolacea (Handschin, 1929)
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu, Odisha*).*
Callyntrura ceylonica (Ritter, 1911) Mitra, and Dallai, 1980
Distribution: India (Kerala).
Callyntrura cingulata (Bonet, 1930)
Distribution: India (Maharashtra).
Callyntrura delamarei Mitra, 1974
Distribution: India (Odisha, Andhra Pradesh*).*
Callyntrura lineata (Parona, 1892) Yosii, 1961
Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Maharashtra, Himachal Pradesh*, Jammu and Kashmir*, West

Bengal*, Andhra Pradesh*, Jharkhand*, Chattisgarh*).

Callyntrura longicornis (Oudemans, 1890)
Distribution: India (Assam, Sikkim, Chattisgarh*).*
Callyntrura carli (Handschin, 1929) Yosii, 1982
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Callyntrura nigerrima (Prabhoo, 1971) Mitra, 1974
Distribution: India (Kerala).
Callyntrura prabhooi Mitra, 1974
Distribution: India (Kerala).
Callyntrura serrata (Salmon, 1957)
Distribution: India (Sikkim, Andhra Pradesh*, Nagaland*, Tripura*, Chattisgarh*).*
Callyntrura sudindica (Prabhoo, 1971) Mitra, 1974
Distribution: India (Kerala, Uttar Pradesh*).*
Callyntrura fissisetosa (Handschin, 1929)
Distribution: India (Tamil Nadu).
Callyntrura variabilis Mitra, 1974
Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh*).*
Callyntrura vestita (Handschin, 1925) Yosii, 1982
Distribution: India (West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh*, Assam, Manipur*, Meghalaya, Nagaland*, Maharashtra*, Chattisgarh*, Jharkhand*).*
Callyntrura zaheri Mitra, 1974
Distribution: India (West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh*, Chattisgarh*).*
Callyntrura japonica (Kinoshita)
Distribution: India (Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur*, Meghalaya*, Mizoram*, Uttarakhand*, Andhra Pradesh*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).*

Genus *Cyphoderopsis* Carpenter, 1917
Cyphoderopsis gracilis Carpenter, 1924
Distribution: India (Meghalaya).
Cyphoderopsis ceylonica Yosii, 1966
Distribution: India (Meghalaya, West Bengal*, Maharashtra*).*
Cyphoderopsis sixocellata Yosii, 1966
Distribution: India (Maharashtra).
Cyphoderopsis decemoculata Prabhoo, 1971
Distribution: India (Kerala).
Cyphoderopsis kempii Carpenter, 1917
Distribution: India (Meghalaya).

Genus *Dicranocentroides* Imms, 1912
Dicranocentroides fasciculatus Imms, 1912
Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Sikkim*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Manipur*, Mizoram*, Nagaland*, Tripura*, Uttar Pradesh*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).*
Dicranocentroides flavescens Yosii, 1966
Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, West Bengal, Manipur*, Maharashtra*, Mizoram*, Nagaland*, Sikkim*, Tripura*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Uttar Pradesh*).*
Dicranocentroides indica (Handschin, 1929)
Distribution: India (Assam, Meghalaya, Manipur*, Mizoram*, Nagaland*, Arunachal Pradesh*,

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Sikkim*, Uttar Pradesh*, Andhra Pradesh*, Chattisgarh*).

Dicranocentroides gisini Mitra, 1975

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, Nagaland*, Odisha*).

Dicranocentroides salmoni Mitra, 1975

Distribution: India (Assam, Meghalaya, Sikkim, Manipur*, Mizoram*, Nagaland*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Uttar Pradesh*, Uttarakhand*).

Dicranocentroides duduaensis Hazra and Mandal, 2015

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Genus *Idiomerus* Imms, 1912

Idiomerus pallidus Imms, 1912

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Lepidonella* Yosii, 1960

Lepidonella ceylonica (Yosii, 1966) Dehanverg, and Bedos, 1995

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Lepidonella duodecimoculata (Prabhoo, 1971)

Dehaveng, and Bedos, 1995

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Tribe *Cremastocephalini* Handschin, 1926

Genus *Pseudosalina* Mitra, 1974

Pseudosalina christianseni Mitra, 1974

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh*).

Pseudosalina multiformis Mitra, 1974

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh*, Andhra Pradesh*).

Pseudosalina nigrocephala (Mitra, 1966)

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh*).

Pseudosalina rapoportii Mitra, 1974

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh*).

Genus *Salina* MacGillivray, 1894

Salina bengalensis Mitra, 1973

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Maharashtra*).

Salina bincinctoides Yosii, 1960

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Salina biformis, Mitra, 1966

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh *, Uttar Pradesh*).

Salina bulbosa (Salmon, 1957) Mitra, 1993

Distribution: India (Sikkim).

Salina celebensis (Schaeffer, 1898) Yosii, 1959

Distribution: India (Assam, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal*).

Salina choudhuriai Mitra, 1973

Distribution: India (Meghalaya).

Salina dubiosa Denis, 1936

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Salina grieta Tyagi and Baijal, 1979

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Salina indica (Imms, 1912) Yosii, 1960

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Maharashtra*, Uttarakhand*, Himachal Pradesh*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Salina javana (Handschin, 1928) Yayuk, 1989

Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Salina montana (Imms, 1912)

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Maharashtra*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Salina quattuorfasciata (Handschin, 1928)

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu).

Salina sikkimensis Mitra, 1973

Distribution: India (Sikkim).

Salina striata (Handschin, 1928)

Distribution: India (Nilgiri, Tamil Nadu, West Bengal, Uttarakhand*, Andaman and Nicobar Islands*).

Salina tricolor (Handschin, 1928)

Distribution: India (Kerala, Uttarakhand*, Manipur*).

Salina yosii Salmon, 1964

Distribution: India (Odisha, West Bengal*).

Genus *Troglopedetes* Absolon, 1907, nec Joseph, 1872

Troglopedetes rasendrans Bhattacharjee, 1985

Distribution: India (Meghalaya).

Genus *Yosiiia* Mitra, 1967

Yosiiia dehradunia Mitra, 1967

Distribution: India (Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh*, Jharkhand*, Tripura*, Arunachal Pradesh*, Sikkim*).

Order *Symphyleona* Börner, 1901 sensu Massoud, 1971

Family *Arrhopalitidae* Stach, 1956

Genus *Pygmarrhopalites* Vargovitsh, 2009

Pygmarrhopalites habei (Yosii, 1965) Vargovitsh, 2009

Distribution: India (Sikkim, Uttar Pradesh*).

Family *Bourletiellidae* Börner, 1912, Sensu Bretfeld, 1994

Genus *Bourletiella* Banks, 1899

Bourletiella captis Baijal and Mathur, 1969

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Bourletiella arvalis (Fitch, 1862)

Distribution: India (Jammu and Kashmir).

Bourletiella hortensis (Fitch, 1863)

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Genus *Prorastriopes* Delamare Deboutteville, 1947

Prorastriopes spathaceus (Börner, 1907)

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Family *Collophoridae* Bretfeld, G, 1999

Genus *Collophora* Richards, Delamare Deboutteville and Masood, 1964

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Collophora remanei Delamare Deboutteville, and Massoud, 1964

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Collophora mysticiosa Yosii, 1960

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Family Dicyrtomidae Börner, 1906

Subfamily Dicyrtominae Richards, 1968

Genus *Calvatomina* Yosii, 1966

Calvatomina bombayensis (Yosii, 1966)

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Calvatomina cruciata (Yosii, 1966)

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Calvatomina pagoda (Yosii, 1966)

Distribution: India (West Bengal).

Calvatomina pallida (Yosii, 1966)

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh*).

Calvatomina trivandran (Prabhoo, 1971)

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Family Katiannidae Börner, 1913 **Sensu, Bretfeld, 1949**

Genus *Sminthurinus* Börner, C., 1901

Sminthurinus trinotatus Axelson, 1905

Distribution: India (Kerala, Uttar Pradesh*).

Subfamily Ptenothricinae Richards, 1968

Genus *Ptenothrix* Börner, 1906

Ptenothrix keralae Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Family Neelidae Folsom, 1896

Genus *Neelus* Folsom, 1896

Neelus murinus Folsom, 1896

Distribution: India (Kerala, West Bengal, Maharashtra).

Family Sminthuridae Lubbock, 1862, **Sensu Deharven*^g, 2004**

Subfamily Sminthurinae Lubbock, 1862, **Sensu Deharven*^g, 2004**

Genus *Pararrhopalites* Bonet and Tellez, 1947

Pararrhopalites anops Bonet and Tellez, 1947

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Pararrhopalites indianus Baijal and Agarwal, 1972

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Genus *Sminthurus* Latreille in Sonnini (1802)

Sminthurus giantensis Baijal and Kohli, 1972

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Sminthurus hamtaensis Baijal, 1958

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Sminthurus kuluensis Baijal, 1958

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Sminthurus parvullus Ritter, 1911

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Kerala, West Bengal*).

Sminthurus pseudoviolaceus Ritter, 1911

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

Sminthurus viridis (Linn. 1758) Bourlet, 1843

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Kerala, West Bengal*).

Genus *Temeritas* Richards in Delamare Deboutteville and Massoud, 1963

Temeritas bharatensis Baijal and Kohli, 1972

Distribution: India (Himachal Pradesh).

Temeritas dimna Mandal, Suman and Bhattacharya, 2016

Distribution: India (Jharkhand).

Subfamily Sphyrothecinae Betsch, 1980

Genus: *Parasphyrotheca* Salmon, 1951

Parasphyrotheca submagnificata Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Genus *Sphyrotheca* Börner, 1906

Sphyrotheca gangetica Yosii, 1966

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh*).

Family Sminthuridae Börner, 1906

Genus *Sminthurides* Börner, 1900

Sminthurides antennatus Baijal and Verma, 1986

Distribution: India (Uttar Pradesh).

Sminthurides velli Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Sminthurides appendiculatus Imms, 1912

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh*).

Sminthurides parvulus (Krausbauer, 1898)

Distribution: India (West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh*).

Genus *Sphaeridia* Linnaniemi, 1912

Sphaeridia indica Prabhoo, 1971

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Sphaeridia biniserrata (Salmon) 1951 Massoud, 1964

Distribution: India (Kerala).

Sphaeridia pumilis (Krausbauer, 1898), Agrell, 1934

Distribution: India (Maharashtra, Kerala, West Bengal).

Genus *Stenacidia* Börner, 1906

Stenacidia violacea (Reuter, 1878)

Distribution: India (Maharashtra).

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